

8T – Objects in Class

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Abstract:

By analyzing the main features of the 8T it is possible to present the main ideas of the framework as object in class. The first class is the class of Bosons that is infinite, and form a non-abelian group. In this analysis we ignore the numerical value and use the number as a reference to an object. The second class is the class of universes, which has infinite objects. Analysis of the kind of objects is presented. Author predict that all the universes are of the same kind, nature minimize the kind of objects it generates.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matric tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2.A) By (1.2.A) those manifolds are topologically invariant with opposite curvature orientations. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^K \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2. A)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it in the fine structure constant formula:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matrix tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

We have presented the spin classification in the 8T thesis, page seventeen, while using the prime critical line:

Spin 0: $2N_0$ variations

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3$ variations

Spin 1: $2N_0 + 3 + N_V$ variations

Spin N = $2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \dots$ variations

Up to this point was introduction, reader is probably familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. **From here** on out, we have a completely **new paper**. up to this day we have taken Bosons to be discrete amount of curvature which is prime and belong to the ring of real integers. Such view comes to an agreement with the ideas behind Quantum mechanics. The discrete amounts and the terms with one net variation are time invariant, that is contrast to composite interactions such as gravity. Composite interaction can contain many distinct combinations with keep the spin invariant. Now, the author would like to analyze the 8T construction n from a different angle, which is more mathematical and maybe do not have any physical meaning, and that is representing the Bosons as objects in class. That way we ignore the numerical values as numeric and regard them as different objects of the same class. The objects differ from one other, but not in quanta but the numbers serve as classification to the object not as numerical value. That is another way to analyze the 8T construction. In a certain sense it is valid to analyze the 8T according to such view, as the Bosons are different fingers of the same hand, they are all part of the ever changing geometry of space time. At high energy they can turn into one another, as proven in the thesis.

To make it more mathematically rigorous we can put the idea of Bosons as objects in class.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{B} &\Rightarrow \{N_{V_1} \dots N_{V_K}\} \\ K &\in \mathbb{R} \\ N_{V_1} &\neq N_{V_2} \dots \end{aligned}$$

The two operations we used, or can use on this class are multiplication and addition. In the operation of addition, we combined net curvature of distinct amount to reach higher distinct primes, in such way we created the gravitational term. That was the idea that allows us the associate the nature of Bosons to non-abelian group. In the context of the idea of object in class, that is mean that the class has infinite objects. In the operation of multiplication, we have combined net variations of certain amount and reached equivalence between addition and multiplication, so the author presented the idea of Quadratic curvature whose physical meaning is unclear.

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 + 13 + 7 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (3)] + 25$$

Now, those primes were chosen in order to make a point, the total sum of the three primes is equivalent to a photon squared.

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 25 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (3)] + \gamma^2$$

The photon squared can be decomposed to matter and anti-matter:

$$\gamma = \pm 5$$

Instead of looking at the actual number, we can again state that the combination of three object in class are equal to one object multiplied and that each object in the class has an inverse object yielding a unitary object, that is synonymous with anti-matter. The universe itself is an object in a class, the class of stationary manifolds flattening each other via areas of extremum curvatures. The objects in the class of universes are also infinite and ever increasing, but the class is the same for all, it obeys the same rules and the same sub-objects, i.e. Bosons appear in the same order of each sub-element, i.e. universe. That is because the invariance of the prime ring under time shifts. We can define the class of universes; each universe is a manifold of the same class, Lorentz with (3,1) signature:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{S} &\Rightarrow \{s_1 \dots s_n\} \\ s_1 &\equiv s_2 \dots \equiv s_n \\ n &\rightarrow \infty \end{aligned}$$

It is implicitly assumed that there is only one class of universes, but whether that is actually the case is unknown. However it is reasonable to assume that nature would generate the minimal number of distinct elements, which is one, rather than maximal amount of distinct elements. Another point that is important is that if each manifold in the packet would be different in kind, the flattening or the interaction between each two manifold pairs with opposite curvature orientation could lead to complications as the manifolds are different. It was implicitly assumed that nature is oriented to the minima in the kind of manifolds it generate, and if one manifold is Lorentz manifold so does the rest.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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